

Design of the fiber-winding lightweight structure inspired by beetle elytra and its mechanical properties

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Abstract: Based on the microstructure of the cross-section of the beetle elytra, a kind of bio-inspired lightweight structures with fiber-winding was designed and made by the carbon fiber material. The mechanical and thermal properties of the lightweight structures were studied with finite element method. At the same time, the quasi-static compression experiment was carried out. The experimental result and the finite element analysis result were compared and analyzed, which proved the effectiveness of the finite element analysis. Furthermore, the mechanical properties of two kinds of structure units with the different fiber winding pattern were analyzed and compared, the results showed the structure with two layers of different fiber-winding patterns is better to improve its mechanical performance.

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Introduction

As technology advances, many industries put forward the new requirements to the materials (higher specific intensity, specific rigidity, damage resistance), and many traditional materials and structures can not meet industry requirements again. However, natural biological materials formed many unique features through 35 million years of evolution in order to adapt to the environment and satisfy the functional requirements with capabilities such as strong toughness, functional adaptability and wound healing capabilities, et al, which are unsurpassed by conventional artificial materials[1]. Now people try to get inspiration from nature to develop new bio-inspired composite materials and structures through learning and imitating some features and functions of biological structure. Since the 1980s, significant progress has been made in understanding the structures and its special functions of the biological composite materials and the bionic research. Mehmet et al[2] studied the composite structure and the mechanical mechanism of pearl shell layer's cross-section, which has been used to develop the new ceramic matrix polymer and ceramic-metal composites, and found that the fracture toughness of new materials improved 40% more than the conventional ones. According to the bamboo structure feature with dense outside and sparse inside, Sun et al [3] manufactured double-layer carbon fiber materials coated with Cu-Fe, Cu-Ni, i.e. CF / Cu -Fe, CF / Cu-Ni composites material, and the bending strength and electrical properties of new composite material are significantly improved comparing with CF / Cu composite materials with the similar carbon fiber volume fraction V_f . Gordon et al [4] used the composite columns, plates and sandwich materials to imitate the spiral structure found in wood cells and made glass fiber/epoxy composite materials, found that its fracture toughness is also significantly improved.

Beetle is a very large population in the nature , and

their former wing in the evolutionary process slowly evolved into elytra with high strength and fracture toughness [5-6] to protect the body of the beetle, or to prevent the body moisture to evaporate and to resist the impact of the outside pressure, etc. The beetle serve as a good bionic object for geometric design and material optimum because of the excellent properties of the elytra such as lightweight, higher specific intensity, etc. Chen et al [7-9] studied the cross-section structure and surface microstructure of hercules beetle, and pointed out that the elytra is a sandwich structure with small columns as bridge peers to connect the top and bottom layers. The columns are arranged as polygon cylinder in elytra, constituting network structure with internal film to enhance the strength and fracture toughness of elytra. Based on the microstructure of the tumblebug's elytra, Chen [10] fabricated a kind of composite laminate with biomimetic fibre helicoidally rounding hole through a special mould and moulding process and the extrusion strength of the biomimetic fibre helicoidally rounding hole was also investigated. Yang [11-12] observed the cross-section microstructure of cybister elytra and measured the tensile strength of the elytra, the experimental results showed that the elytra cross-section is composed of cavities, fiber bundles that connect inner layers to the outer cuticular layers, several chitin fiber layers and a dense black epicuticle. The tensile test of the elytra showed that it has high specific strength.

In this paper, on the basis of the microstructure of the cross-section of Cybister (Cybister tripunctatus Olivier) elytra, a bio-mimetic structure with the fiber winding was designed, and its mechanical properties were studied with finite element method. Also, a sample of the epoxy resin based carbon fiber material was built, and the quasi-static compression experiment was carried out to compare to the FEM result and prove the accuracy and reliability of the FEM model. Furthermore, the different fiber winding patterns were suggested and the effects of the winding pattern on its mechanical properties

were analyzed, the results showed the structure with two different fiber-winding patterns has better mechanical performance than that of the structure with only one fiber-winding pattern.

1. Bionic design of the lightweight structure

Microstructure features of the cross-section of *Cybister* elytra.

The microstructure of the cross-section and the mechanical properties of the beetle elytra have been studied by many researchers [13-18]. Fig.1 is the microstructure of the cross-section of *cybister* elytra, it is a typical sandwich structure, and is composed of cavities, fiber bundles acting as bridge piers, several chitin fiber layers and a dense black epicuticle. The fiber bundles are braided in the parallel, perpendicular and spatial helix ways, which improve the mechanical properties of elytra, such as intensity, toughness, and peeling resistance, et al. The thickness of the epicuticle, a single chitin fiber layer, the average diameter of cavities and the inner diameter of the hollow bridge pier are 12, 2, 80–95 and 30–40 μm , respectively. The cavities in the elytra effectively reduce the structure weight over a span of about 250 μm . According to references [11,12], the *Cybister* elytra have a duty ratio (cavity area to elytra area) of about 22% and density of $0.89 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$, while their average hardness and Young's modulus are 0.48 and 8.21 GPa respectively, and their transverse and longitudinal tensile strengths are as high as 169.2 ± 22.5 and $194.5 \pm 23.4 \text{ MPa}$ respectively.

1.2 Structural design inspired by beetle elytra

According to the morphological features of the *cybister* elytra, also referring to the model suggested by Chen [8], a bio-mimetic lightweight structure featured by cavities and hollow columns which are composed of fibers braided in different patterns was suggested, and the number of fiber layers and the orientations of fibers are shown in the cross-section of column (Fig. 3).

2. The mechanical analysis of the bionic lightweight structure

2.1 Quasi-static compression analysis

2.1.1 FEM analysis of compression strength of the structure

Finite element modeling

To simplify FEM model, firstly, the structure composed of layers of fibers with the orientation paralleled to the axis of column and paralleled horizontally in the upper and bottom planes was built and analyzed. The overall size of the model is $30 \times 30 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$, and the thickness of the upper and bottom plane, the inner diameter of the small column and the wall thickness are 1.5mm, 3.5mm and 0.5mm, respectively. 3D model of the structures was built with pro/E software and then transferred into ANSYS Workbench environment, the finite element type was Solid 186, and the total numbers of nodes and elements of the structure are 60659, 31215 respectively, as shown in Fig. 4. The material of the model was epoxy resin based carbon fiber composite, the same material was used to build the structure samples. The material constants were set as Table 1.

Load and boundary constraints

Similar to the load and boundary constraints in the quasi-static compression experiment of the honeycomb structure [19], displacement was applied as a load to the top surface of the model step by step. Here, the number of load steps should be chosen reasonably. The model bottom was fixed for all six degrees of freedom (DOFs).

Results analysis

The compression force corresponding to the displacement of each sub-step was obtained through finite element analysis, then, the force–displacement curve was determined (Fig. 5). It can be seen that the compression force initially increased with the displacement, however, when the compression force reached the critical yield limit, the force changed little as the displacement continued to increase, demonstrating the structure had already reached the elastic–plastic stage, and its compression limit load is 12.7KN. According to the

equation $\sigma=F/A$, where F is the compression limit load (N), and A is the area to bear the load (mm^2), the compression strength of the structure is 14.1 MPa. Taking the average density of the structure into account, the specific compression strength is 40.3 [$\text{MPa}/(\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3})$].

2.1.2 Experimental verification of FEM analysis

In order to verify the reliability of the finite element analysis, the structural samples were built from the epoxy resin based carbon fiber material (Fig.6), and a quasi-static compression experiment was performed on an electronic universal testing machine with load changing between 0 and 100 KN (Changchun, China).

The quasi-static compression is a single-direction force produced by moving the pressure head with a constant velocity of 1 mm/min. The force produced on the pressure head and the displacement due to the compression deformation of the sample were recorded and monitored by sensors. The test results showed that the compression limit load is 11.6 KN. Comparing with the FEM result, the error is 9.5%, the difference mainly come from the glue connections between the columns and the top and bottom plates in the structural samples, which is not considered in the FEM model, but definitely reduce the compression ability of samples. Fig.6 compares the experimental curve with the FEM analysis curve. Although there is a difference between the experimental and analytical results, especially the force of the experimental curve sharply declined after reaching a maximum owing to the structural fracture, while the force indicated by the analytical curve declined gently, it is seen that the experimental results are in accordance with the analysis results at the first stage, demonstrating the effectiveness and reliability of the finite element method analysis.

2.2 Shear strength analysis

FEM model

The same 3D model in section 2.1 was used again. According to the reference [20], the bottom plane of the model was fixed for all six degrees of freedom,

and the upper plane is defined as the rigid plane without any deformation, and in-plane horizontal force was applied as the shear force in Fig. 7(a). The material constants are just the same as in Table 1.

Results analysis

The force and the corresponding displacement in each sub-step were obtained through finite element analysis, and the shear force–displacement curve was determined as shown in Fig. 7(b). According to the equation $\tau=F_{\max}/A$ and equation $G_{\text{eq}}=1000\times\delta\times\theta/A$, where F_{\max} is the maximum shear force (N), and A is the original area to bear the force (mm^2), δ is the original thickness of the sample (mm), and θ is the linear slope of the straight-line fitting of the linear part of the curve (N/mm). Then, the shear strength of the bionic structure τ is 1.8 MPa, and the equivalent shear modulus G_{eq} is 94.1Mpa.

The FEM results showed that the bio-mimetic structure has excellent mechanical properties, its specific compression strength is 40.3 kN m/kg, which is much higher than the values of 4~16 kN m/kg for stainless-steel hollow-sphere foam and Al foam [21], and its shear strength is 1.8 MPa, shear modulus is 94.1Mpa, both are greater than the values of T722 Nomex honeycomb structure ($\tau=1.56$ Mpa and $G_{\text{eq}}=59.2$ Mpa) [22].

3. The effect of different fiber winding patterns on the mechanical properties of the structure

As mentioned above, the fiber bundles of cybister's elytra are braided in the parallel, perpendicular and spatial helix ways, which improve the mechanical properties of elytra, and the designed bio-mimetic structure in this paper also is braided in fibers with two different patterns. So, it is necessary to further analyze the effect of the fiber winding patterns on the mechanical properties of the structure.

3.1 3D FEM model

Here, the small hollow column with two different fiber winding patterns was built as the FEM model, and two fiber winding patterns include the parallel

and the spatial helical patterns. In Fig. 8, the column was wrapped in two layers of fibers, (a) is composed of one layer of vertically paralleled fiber and one layer of the spatial helical fiber, and the helix angle is 65° . (b) is composed of two layers of vertically paralleled fibers. The finite element type was Solid 186, the material was the same as that of the bionic structure, material constants can be referred to Table 1.

3.2 Comparison of the mechanical properties of two columns

The quasi-static compression and shear strength of two columns were analyzed and compared with FEM. The load and boundary constraints of the quasi-static compression analysis were the same as those mentioned in section 2.1, and the load and boundary constraints of the shear strength analysis were defined as [23]: the top plate of the model was fixed for all six degrees of freedom, while the bottom plate was fixed axially, and horizontally shear force is applied to the middle part of the model. The compression force–displacement curve and the shear force-displacement curve were determined as shown in Fig. 9~10.

It can be seen from Fig.9~Fig.10 that the shear strength of the column wrapped in the vertically paralleled fibers and the spatial helical fibers was greater than that of the column with two layers of vertically paralleled fibers, while the compression strength of the former was smaller than that of the latter, demonstrating the fiber braided in the vertically paralleled ways is more suitable to bear the compression force. Thus, the bio-mimetic structure with two different braiding patterns could

possess both mechanical advantages, and has better mechanical properties.

4. Conclusions

A bio-mimetic lightweight structure inspired by the cybister elytra was designed, and its mechanical properties were studied with finite element method. The compression force–displacement curve and the shear force-displacement curve of this structure were obtained, which demonstrated it has great mechanical properties. At the same time, a sample built with the epoxy resin based carbon fiber material was made, and the quasi-static compression experiment was carried out to verify the reliability of the FEM method. Furthermore, the effects of the different fiber winding patterns on the structure mechanical properties were investigated, the results showed the different fiber winding patterns are suitable to bear the different kind of loads. So, it is quite reasonable that there exist different fiber winding patterns in the biological structure, and this brings new ideas for the design of the new lightweight structures.

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Fig. 1. Microstructures of the cross-section of elytra. EPI, Epicuticle; FL, Fiber layers; CAV, Cavity; BP, Bridge pier.

Fig. 2. Fiber layers of the cross-section of elytra. (a) Fiber layers; (b) Fibers orientation. FL: Fiber layer; Arrows point to the fiber laying direction.

Fig. 3. Elytra inspired lightweight structure
 (a) The bio-mimetic structure; (b) The cross-section structure of single hollow column. EP: Laminated plate; FL: spiral fiber layer; FB: vertical fiber layer; HS: cavity; H: column holes

Fig.4. The finite element model of the bio-mimetic structure

Fig. 5. Comparison of the experimental results with the finite

Fig. 6. The bionic structural sample

(a)

(b)

Fig.7. FEM analysis of the shear strength of the bio-mimetic structure
 (a) FEM of the structure; (b) The shear force–displacement curve of the structure

Fig.8. The column with the different fiber winding patterns
 (a) vertically paralleled fiber + spatial helical fiber (b) two vertically paralleled fibers

Fig.9. The compression force–displacement curve

Fig.10. The shear force–displacement curve

Table 1 the material properties of the model

material	elastic modulus (GPa)	Density (g/cm ³)	Tensile strength (MPa)
carbon fiber	253	1.78	4980
SU810 epoxy resin	2.5	1.2	55

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